

HOSPITAL PROXIMITIES TO NEARBY BROADCAST STATIONS

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Abstract

A technique for identifying hospital locations which are potentially subject to high intensity radio-frequency fields from nearby broadcast stations is discussed. A medical care facilities data base representing 27 percent of all existing such facilities in the United States was used in conjunction with an automated broadcast station data base to determine and analyze distances between hospitals and nearby stations. It was determined that 20 percent of all hospitals are located within one mile of at least one FM broadcast station. The closest observed separation distance was 0.02 mile. Data are presented which allow determination of the fraction of hospitals having minimum separation distances \leq various values for AM, FM, and TV stations. Information is provided on the number of such stations found within one mile of each hospital studied and the total effective radiated power of these stations.

Introduction

This paper reports on the use of computer automated data bases to examine the proximity of hospitals to nearby broadcast stations. The Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) has for several years endeavored to identify particular locations throughout the United States (US) which are potentially illuminated with high intensity radiofrequency fields in connection with EPA's program for evaluation of nonionizing radiation hazards. Previous studies have reported on several such identification techniques^{1,2,3,4} and this paper presents yet another approach to the problem.

Automated data bases of US broadcast stations and medical care facilities were prepared for convenient machine based analysis. The two data bases were then merged and an analysis was accomplished which identified hospital locations that were close to adjacent broadcast stations. Our use of a medical care facilities data base in demonstrating this identification procedure was prompted by the current interest in the electromagnetic compatibility (EMC) of medical devices commonly used in such facilities. Several investigators have studied the hospital electromagnetic field environment in particular^{5,6} with reference to device susceptibility. Vreeland et al.⁷ have examined the specific problem of broadcast fields from the standpoint of interference to cardiac pacemakers and interference with the operation of a digital electronic thermometer has been observed in the presence of strong FM radio-signals⁸. The Bureau of Medical Devices within the Food and Drug Administration (FDA), recognizing the apparent need for device EMC control, has recently developed an EMC standard for medical devices⁹ which prescribes among other things minimum radiated electric field susceptibility limits. A question of hospital proximity to broadcast transmitters plays an integral roll in the rationale for this part of the FDA EMC standard. This report presents data which is pertinent to the FDA's rationale.

Description of Data Bases

The broadcast station data base used in this analysis was obtained in several parts from the Federal Communications Commission (FCC). Separate data files were obtained and after a period of editing and merging a data base suitable for this analysis was developed. The separate data files obtained consisted of: (a) an AM engineering data base, (b) an FM engineering data base, (c) a TV engineering data base, and (d) the entire broadcast portion of the FCC Master File. To arrive at a useable file which contained unique records of broadcast stations which are actually on-the-air and which contained the necessary technical parameters for each station rather extensive editing of these separate files was performed. We used the engineering data bases as a fundamental building block because of their currency and general inclusion of technical data necessary for our analysis which is not maintained in the Master File. For example, the engineering data bases for each type of station, be it AM, FM, or TV contains information for stations which are in the process of applying for a license as well as those actually on the air and even entries for stations holding construction permits (CP). Records for stations other than those actually permitted to broadcast were deleted, this process being somewhat tedious for those stations indicated as holding a CP in that some stations have authority to broadcast under a CP while others do not. Reference had to be made to manually kept lists of such broadcast authorizations at the FCC to clarify this matter.

Another problem in the original files was that the aural carrier power for television stations is not kept in the TV engineering data base and in this instance, aural carrier power data was extracted from the Master File to enhance the TV engineering data base. A similar problem existed with the AM engineering data base in that it is not yet complete for all AM radio stations. Again use of the Master File provided the necessary information. After our careful preparation of a single consistent data base we found that the indicated number of broadcast stations actually on-the-air as of December 1, 1977, was 9387. These were partitioned by class as follows:

<u>Type of Station</u>	<u>Number on-the-air</u>
AM Standard Broadcast	4574
FM Radio	3829
TV VHF and UHF	984

For each station our edited data base contains the station call sign, frequency, latitude and longitude, power (both horizontal and vertical polarization components for FM and both visual and aural for TV), the city and state in which the station is located, and the height above average terrain (HAAT) for FM and TV stations.

A medical care facilities data base was obtained from the Federal Preparedness Agency¹⁰. This computer accessible file contains information on 7364 medical care facilities throughout the US. To our knowledge

this represents slightly more than all such facilities recognized by the American Hospital Association (AHA) as of January 1975. The AHA Guide to the Health Care Field¹¹ indicates that there were 7082 health care facilities in the US as of January 1, 1977. The data base contains extensive information on each facility, including for example, the pertinent city/state, the facility name, the latitude and longitude, the rated total bed capacity, average daily patient census, personnel figures, type of services provided, and a location accuracy code. This code, generated by the FPA, describes the supposed accuracy of the indicated coordinates for the facility. For the 7364 facilities in the total data base we analyzed the location accuracy codes and found that there were 2271 facilities, or 31 percent, which were classified as having the highest accuracy, this being stated by FPA as being within 200 meters of the indicated coordinates. Table 1 provides a breakdown of this analysis. For the purpose of this analysis we elected to use only those facilities which had the most accurately specified coordinates. This was done in the interest of obtaining the most accurate results for identification of extremely close proximity situations.

TABLE 1. ANALYSIS OF 7364 HEALTH CARE FACILITY LOCATION ACCURACY CODES

Accuracy Code	Description	No. in Class	Percent in Class
1	0-200 m	2271	30.8
2	200-500 m	1666	22.6
3	500-1500 m	1196	16.2
4	SLA*	36	0.5
5	Zip Code**	2195	29.8

*SLA=standard location area, coordinates in this class are for the nominal center of the SLA

**Coordinates for this class were for the post office serving the zip code of the given facility

After examining the types of services provided by each facility we took the liberty of further deleting certain facilities from consideration in the analysis. Table 2 shows the various types of services and those which we chose to delete because of the lower probability of significant use of critical life support instrumentation and/or equipment. After deletion of those facilities with particular services we obtained a final computing data base of 2000 facilities which met our requirement of having the best determined coordinates and also most likely to make use of critical equipment. It is our estimation that this number represents about 27 percent of all health care facilities in the US recognized by the AHA.

Method of Analysis

Our procedure of analysis consisted simply of the following: for each of the 2000 hospital facilities used in the study, a computation of the distance to each AM, FM, and TV station in our broadcast data base was made. For each class of station, the station found to be the closest to the hospital was noted as was its distance and power. In the case of FM and TV stations we also retained the HAAT. Additionally we kept record of all stations of each class and their summed power within one mile of the hospital. This

particular data was retained because it was felt that such information could form an index of the nearby disposition of multiple transmitter sites.

TABLE 2. HEALTH CARE FACILITY SERVICE TYPE AND INCLUSION OR DELETION FROM ANALYSIS

Type of Service	Included in Analysis	Deleted from Analysis
General medical and surgical	X	
Hospital unit of an institution	X	
Armed forces dispensary		X
Psychiatric		X
Tuberculosis and other respiratory diseases	X	
Narcotic addiction		X
Maternity	X	
Eye, ear, nose, and throat		X
Rehabilitation		X
Orthopedic	X	
Chronic disease		X
Other speciality	X	
Alcoholism		X
Childrens general	X	
Childrens hospital unit of institution	X	
Childrens psychiatric		X
Childrens TB and other respiratory diseases	X	
Childrens eye, ear, nose, and throat		X
Childrens rehabilitation		X
Childrens orthopedic	X	
Childrens other speciality	X	
Osteopathic hospital	X	
Childrens chronic diseases		X

Results

For each class of station the accumulative percentage of hospitals with minimum separation distances (d_{min}) to the nearest broadcast station were plotted as a function of separation distance in Figures 1, 2, and 3. The data are plotted on log-probability paper and visual best fit curves were drawn through the data points. It is interesting to observe the apparent log normal behavior of the fraction of hospitals with d_{min} values \leq the indicated separation distances. Because we have not yet tested the data rigorously, we can not specify a confidence level at which the data is log normally distributed but there is every indication that the data is so distributed at least for AM and FM stations. From the results presented in Figures 1, 2, and 3 we have summarized several pertinent observations in Table 3. For each class of station Table 3 provides the d_{min} values associated with 1, 50 (the median), and 90 percent of the hospitals as well as the percentage of hospitals with d_{min} values \leq 1 mile.

It can be seen that 19 percent of the hospitals analyzed are within 1 mile of at least 1 AM station, 20 percent are within 1 mile of at least 1 FM station, and 2.7 percent are within 1 mile of at least 1 TV station. Also, 1 percent of the hospitals studied were found to be within 0.18 miles of an FM station.

Figure 1. Hospital Proximity to AM Broadcast Stations

Figure 3. Hospital Proximity to TV Broadcast Stations

Figure 2. Hospital Proximity to FM Broadcast Stations

TABLE 3. SUMMARY OF PERTINENT OBSERVATIONS FROM FIGURES 1, 2, AND 3

Class of Station	Separation distance (mi) for various accumulative percentages of hospitals			Percent hospitals with $d_{\min} \leq 1$ mile
	1%	50%	90%	
AM	0.25	2.29	7.59	19
FM	0.18	2.51	11.22	20
TV	0.56	10.00	35.48	2.7

Table 4 summarizes the results of analyzing the total effective radiated power (ERP) of all stations identified as being within 1 mile of each class of station. It is interesting to note that 3 hospitals studied are located within 1 mile of a total accumulative ERP of TV stations of between 10 and 100 MW.

TABLE 4. NUMBER OF HOSPITALS WITH VARIOUS TOTAL ERP WITHIN 1 MILE

Total ERP of stations within 1 mile (kW)		No. of hospitals with total ERP within 1 mile		
		AM	FM	TV
10000	- 100000	-	-	3
1000	- 10000	-	1	13
100	- 1000	-	102	44
10	- 100	9	110	6
1	- 10	226	86	-
.1	- 1	17	19	-
.01	- .1	-	80	-
	<.01	<u>1748</u>	<u>1602</u>	<u>1934</u>
TOTAL		2000	2000	2000

Note: There are 6 hospitals with a 50 kW AM station within 1 mile

Table 5 is provided to illustrate the type of computer data output obtained in this study. This table comprises a list of hospitals, ordered by increasing d_{min} values for the first 60 hospitals having smallest d_{min} values. Each line of Table 5 contains a sequence of data which may be decoded by referring to the notes found in the following chart:

<u>Date Field</u>	<u>Description</u>
1	Sequence Code
2	Hospital Name
3	City
4	State
5	Type of Service Code
6	Government or Non-Government Code
7	Length of Stay Code
8	Total Number of Beds
9	Daily Patient Census
10	Total Personnel (Full Plus Part Time)
11	Station Class Code (1=AM, 2=TV, 3=FM)
12	Call Sign of Closest Station
13	Minimum Separation Distance (Miles)
14	Frequency (MHZ) (MHz)
15	Total ERP of Closest Station
16	HAAT of Closest Station
17	Number of Stations of Same Class Within 1 Mile
18	Total ERP of Stations Within 1 Mile

In view of the associated accuracy of the hospital coordinates used in this study it is not possible to assign an absolutely proper order to the indicated hospitals with distances shown less than 0.12 miles. Thus if one were to individually check each hospital by actually measuring the distance between it and the nearby station, a reordering of the indicated d_{min} values might occur. Also we caution that there is always the possibility of inherent error in each data base used in that despite our careful attention to insure accuracy, a hospital may no longer be at the indicated location or that a station may have erroneously indicated coordinates. We believe, though, that the results can be interpreted certainly as representative of the hospital-station proximity relationship.

Summary

A method of identifying hospital sites with the potential for high intensity radiofrequency fields has been described. Two data bases consisting of both AM, FM, and TV broadcast stations and medical care facilities in the US were prepared for a subsequent computer examination of the minimum separation distances between each hospital and the nearest broadcast station. Using a subset of the health care facility data base of some 2000 hospitals and a broadcast station inventory of 9387 stations it was found that 18 percent of all hospitals are located within 1 mile of an AM station, 20 percent within a mile of an FM station and 2.7 percent within a mile of a TV station. It is interesting to note that these figures can be taken as representative for AM and FM stations at the 1500 meter (.93 mile) distance suggested by FDA⁹ as being a reasonably probable separation distance for hospitals. The closest indicated separation distance for the hospitals studied was 0.02 miles and this was confirmed by contact with the hospital's administration. The median separation distances, i.e., those distances within which a station is located for half of all hospitals, were found to be 2.29, 2.51, and 10.0 miles for AM, FM, and TV stations respectively. Data are presented which allow determination of the accumulative fraction of hospitals having minimum separation distance \leq than various values. A table is provided which illustrates, for those hospitals determined to be closest to stations, the closest found station, its type, power, and antenna height (if FM or TV), and administrative data specific to the hospital.

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